

ANALYZING SANTAL CREATION MYTH THROUGH THE WRITING OF CAMPBELL'S VERSION OF THE CREATION TRADITION

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ABSTRACT:

This paper narrates and interprets the Santal cosmic myth of Campbell's version. The paper highlights the identity and the traditions that have been passed on from generation to generation. Myth of creation is the central locus for Santal identity. Santal believed that the first human creation in the world were their ancestors. They have remarkable traditions and folklores but didn't have any written records until 19th century. They believe that the legends, songs and folklores were the basis of their origin. The core objectives of this paper is to delineate the creation story, origin of Santal and traditions. The study strives to focus on the worldview of Santal and its culture. The paper seeks to illustrate Andrew Campbell a Scottish missionary's version of cosmology. Written ethnographic accounts by Scottish missionary Andrew Campbell and Norwegian missionaries like Lars Oslenskreftsrud and Paul Olaf Bodding have exerted immense influence on popular myth of creation among the Santals.

KEYWORDS:

COSMIC MYTH, SANTAL, THAKUR JIV, ANDREW CAMPBELL AND MALIN BUDHI.

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INTRODUCTION:

The Santals are one of the well-studied tribes of India. Guhahas grouped them as a race belonging to Proto-Australoid community. Grierson on the basis of their spoken language has placed them to the Austro-Asiatic sub family of the Munda group of language. D.N. Majumdar describes tribes in India as a collection of families or group of families bearing a common name, members of which occupy the same territory, speak the same language and observe the certain taboos regarding marriage, profession or occupation, and have developed a well assigned system of reciprocity and mutuality of obligation. The terms "tribe" and "tribal" are used to refer to populations who claim to have a distinct identity from the Hindu castes. The term tribe has always been a debated topic across Indian academia for various aspects of its distinctive features of identity. For a very long time, tribal societies in India have been considered as societies without history. History being one of the markers through which members of a community identify themselves with a shared past plays a major role in constructing an identity. Yet most distinctive aspect of Jharkhand is the tribal religion, sometimes called SarnaDhorom (sarna being a sacred grove; dhorom is a religion), a system of belief in ancestors and the deities called bongas, which is shared by the Mundari-speaking tribes. SarnaDhorom is not marked by formal institutions, but expressed in family worship of the deities and sacrifices to appease them. The bongas are represented by

stones and trees and dwell in a sacred grove called sarnaby the Munda, dessauliby the Ho, and jaherby the Santal.

ORIGIN OF SANTALS:

The Santals believed that their forefathers were the first human creation in the world. They have remarkable traditions and folklores but didn't have any written records until the 19th century. They believe the traditional songs and folklores are the basis of their origin. At present it is an open question among ethnologists concerning how this ethnic group made its way into the region which it now occupies. The missionary work among the Santals began around 1850 and gradually the missionaries conceived unanimous adaptation of writing the Santali language in Roman script. Horkorean Mare Hapramkoreak Katha, a book regarded as authoritative and frequently referred in Indian Law Courts of the Santal area which was based on the narration of an old Santal Guru Kolean. It was narrated from the mouth of an old Santal Guru Kolean and based on traditions handed down from generation to generation through teaching and verbatim. The book was literally translated into English as "Traditions and Institutions of the Santals" by P.O. Bodding in 1942.

CREATION MYTH ACCORDING TO THE WRITING OF ANDREW CAMPBELL

In the beginning, there was only Thakur Jiv and nothing

existed. There was no land visible except water. Then Thakur Jiv was asked by the servants of him that how shall we create human beings? Thakur Jiv replied If we desire so we can create them. You can create human beings if I bless you. Malin Budhi who would reside in the rock cave under water met Thakur Jiv and got order to create human beings. Thakur Jiv was a spectator. Malin Budhi created human beings some say that she created them of a kind of froth which proceeded from supernatural being who resided at the bottom of the sea. Other say that she created them of stiff clay. After creating human being she laid them out to dry and in the meanwhile SIN SADOW (day horse) trample them under its foot destroys them. After sometime Thakur jiv demanded of Malin Budhi if she prepared them. She replied that I made them but on account of my enemies they were destroyed. Thakur Jiv asked who are your enemy she replied Sin Sadow is my enemy. Then he said to her to kick these pieces into Soranai and SamudNai. He then blessed her to create human beings. Having prepared them, she went to meet him again and told him to give them life. He said above the doorframe is life or spirit of birds do not bring that, upon the sanga (cross beam) is the life of human beings, bring it. So, she went but because of her low stature she could not reach the sanga so she brought the life of birds from the doorframe gave it to them. Sooner they flew up into the sky and continued the course whether for twelve years or twelve months is doubtful. These birds were called Has and Hasil. These birds come to Thakur Jiv and told that you have given us life give us a place to live and rest as well. In the sea, there were many creatures like sole fish, crab, prince earth Worm. Thakur jiv called them and ordered them to raise the earth above the water. Sole Fish was the first to take initiative to raise earth above the water. Even after repeated trail it failed to do perform the obligation. Then crab said I will do it however, it failed to do the same. After that prince earth worm undertook the charge to accomplish it. It put its head under water and swallowed earth which passing through him fell upon the surface of the water but immediately sank to the bottom. It then said if we fasten the prince tortoise at the fur corner with chains and then raise the earth on his back, it will remain and not fall into the water again. After securing prince tortoise with chains the prince earth worm raised the earth on his back and there existed an island in the middle of water. When this event took place Thakur Jiv caused the Karam tree to sprang up and at the foot of the he caused Sirom grass to spring up. After this, Thakur Jiv caused to cover up the earth of all types of tress and herbs. Has and Hasil made on karam tree and afterwards they made their nest among the Sirom grass. Female laid two eggs and Ragop boar came and ate them. This incident happened again and again. Has and Hasil informed this incident to Thakur Jiv that Ragop boar had eaten their eggs sever times. so Thakur Jiv appointed Jaher Era who took care of the birds and their eggs. From the eggs were born a male and a female whose names were pilchu Haram and Pilchu Budhi. Thakur Jiv constituted maran Buru (Great Spirit) their guardian. Pilchu Haram and Pilchu Budhi sustained

on grain of the grasses sumtubukucabd Sama. Maranburu visited them daily. Maran Buru taught them how to make plough so that they can do agriculture. He also taught them how to cultivate paddy, weed and thrash paddy. After the collection of crops are done, they have to offer to maranburu by facing towards East. He then taught how to make rice beer and its whole process like to pound the rice to flour, take Ranu and grind it very fine. When these are done they have to put into a new earthen pot with water and afterwards the liquid was poured off into another vessel and the Ranu ran thrown away. Then directed them to make flour into past with the water in which the Ranu ran had been. When this was done he instructed them to make paste into balls and put them into basket. It should be kept for three days. He then told them to boil rice and dry it and mix ranu powder with the rice. It should be kept for three days in earthen pot sprinkling some water over it. When Maran Buru came to them after three days, he found strong smell and told them to boil water and pour into the earthen pot. The first Santal man and woman prepared liquor from the rice is called Handi. When the evening came, they drank deeply and becoming intoxicated they were brother and sister. The following day they were ashamed and covered themselves with leaves. In the course of time seven sons and seven daughters were born to them and they remained in Hihiri Pipiri till their children grew up.

CRITICISM OF THE SANTAL CREATION MYTH AND ITS COMPARISON WITH SKREFSRUD'S VERSION:

The Santal creation myth penned down by Andrew Campbell differ significantly from that of narrated by Koleanguru. Campbell's version has fewer number of aquatic animals trying to bring up earth from the bottom of the sea than the number given in Skrefsrud's version. Campbell does not talk about the formation of mountains. He states that Karam was the first tree to be grown whereas Skrefsrud says that it was Siron grass. Based on the both creations myth, it is very difficult to state that the Thakur Jiv is almighty. The myth states that it was not only the Thakur Jiv pre-existed but also many creatures already existed before the earth was created. However, to judge the originality of these two versions is a difficult proposition. It is to be noted that Santali writing of early missionaries equated Pilchu Haram and Pilchu Budhi with Adam and Eve. Unlike Santal creation story the creation story of Christian has chronology and clearly defined. The God of Bible is the Omnipotent, Omniscient and Omnipresent whereas the Thakur Jiv is not. Santal creation narrative takes for granted the existence of other supernatural beings who played an important role in the creation.

CONCLUSION:

In this paper, I analyzed the Campbell version of Santal creation story. According to the traditions written by both Campbell and Skrefsrud, the Thakur Jiv is not the almighty and pre-existed. Creation story marks the identity of the Santals through the narration that has been passed on from generation to generation. Creation tradition serves as

a historiography to trace the sociological history of the people anchoring their history in the creation of the world. It also serves as an ethnic history to mark them as distinct people.

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